

Effect of the combination of deferiprone with ethanolic extract of *Phaleria macrocarpa* L. fruit in overcoming iron excess in the liver of hemosiderosis model rats

Rahma¹, Ari Estuningtyas², Kusmardi³, Erni Hernawati Poerwaningsih⁴

¹ Master's Programme in Biomedical Sciences, Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Indonesia, Jakarta, 10430, Indonesia

² Department of Pharmacology and Therapeutics, Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Indonesia, Jakarta, Indonesia

³ Department of Anatomical Pathology, Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Indonesia, Jakarta, 10430, Indonesia

⁴ Department of Medical Pharmacy, Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Indonesia, Jakarta, 10430, Indonesia

Corresponding author: Ari Estuningtyas (aestuningtyas04@gmail.com)

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Abstract

The efficacy of deferiprone (DFP) in reducing liver iron content is still inadequate. Ethanolic extract of *Phaleria macrocarpa* L. (PM) fruit showed iron chelation activity and hepatoprotective effects. This study aimed to evaluate the efficacy of the combination of deferiprone and PM extract to reduce iron content in the liver. Rats were divided into 6 groups: normal, iron overload (IO), IO+DFP, IO+PM extract, IO+PM+DFP normal, or half dose. Rats were induced with iron-dextran injections over 8 weeks, with therapy starting from week 4. Measurements included hepatic iron, malondialdehyde (MDA), GSH, and TNF- α levels, hepatic GPx4 mRNA expression, plasma ALT and AST activity, and histopathology. While none of the treatments significantly reduced hepatic iron, treatment with PM+DFP half dose showed the greatest reduction and improved MDA, ALT, AST, and TNF- α levels compared to DFP monotherapy. GSH and GPx4 mRNA were not significantly altered by the combination therapy.

Keywords

iron chelator, iron overload, deferiprone, *Phaleria macrocarpa*

Introduction

Iron is a crucial micronutrient essential for various biological processes, but excess iron can trigger ferroptosis, a regulated form of cell death that is iron-dependent. This dual role of iron necessitates strict regulatory mechanisms to prevent adverse effects (Zhang et al. 2022). In particular, iron overload can result in the accumulation of free

iron, promoting the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) through the Fenton reaction. Studies have shown that under these conditions, the expression of glutathione peroxidase 4 (GPx4), an antioxidant enzyme, is diminished, leading to disrupted lipid peroxidation cycles and oxidative damage (Chen et al. 2022; Deng et al. 2023).

Thalassemia is the most common cause of secondary iron overload, resulting from increased intestinal absorption

and regular blood transfusions (Wahidiyat et al. 2020; Hsu et al. 2022). The excess iron accumulates mainly in the liver, where it induces ferroptosis, marked by elevated levels of liver enzymes like ALT and AST in the serum (Salama et al. 2022). This process also triggers inflammation through the activation of NF- κ B, which promotes the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines and may lead to hepatic fibrosis (Tang et al. 2021; Salama et al. 2022; Wang et al. 2023).

To prevent organ damage from iron overload, thalassemia patients are often treated with iron chelators like deferoxamine, deferiprone, and deferasirox. However, deferiprone, which is commonly administered to thalassemia major patients, has limited efficacy in reducing liver iron levels and poses risks of hepatotoxicity (Yatmark et al. 2014; Wahidiyat et al. 2018; Olivieri et al. 2019; Verna 2021). Therefore, there is a need for new therapeutic agents that improve efficacy while minimizing side effects.

One promising natural compound for development as an iron chelator is *Phaleria macrocarpa* L. (PM) fruit, which is also known as God's Crown fruit. The ethanolic extract of PM fruit is known to contain the compound mangiferin. At a concentration of 50 mg/kg body weight, mangiferin is capable of preventing iron accumulation in the liver of iron-overloaded rats and enhancing its excretion in the urine (Estuningtyas et al. 2019). Mangiferin is known to exhibit an iron chelation mechanism similar to that of deferiprone, acting as a bidentate ligand capable of forming complexes with iron (Pardo-Andreu et al. 2006). Mangiferin also exerts an antiferroptotic effect by activating the transcription factor Nrf2, leading to an increase in SLC7A11 expression for the synthesis of GSH that is crucial for GPx4 activity (Deng et al. 2023). Additionally, mangiferin exhibits anti-inflammatory effects by inhibiting the synthesis of TNF- α at both the transcriptional and translational levels, as evidenced by a reduction in TNF- α mRNA and protein levels in the liver (Yang et al. 2020b).

Verna already conducted a comparative study on the effects of deferiprone, mangiferin, and ethanolic extracts of PM fruit, which were administered individually in an iron-overloaded rat model (Verna 2021). Due to its iron-chelating ability as well as its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities, the ethanolic extract of PM fruit at a dose of 100 mg/kg body weight may enhance the efficacy and reduce the side effects of deferiprone when administered concurrently. Based on the aforementioned considerations, we are interested in combining PM fruit extract with deferiprone to evaluate its efficacy in reducing liver iron levels in iron-overloaded rats.

Materials and methods

Ethical approval

Ethical approval for this research had been obtained from the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Medicine, University of Indonesia-Cipto Mangunkusumo Hospital (No. KET964/UN2.F1/ETIK/PPM.00.02/2022).

Experimental animals and sample size

Animals used in this study were healthy male Sprague-Dawley rats of \pm 8 weeks old with an average body weight of 200–250 grams. The animals were obtained from the Indonesian Food And Drug Authority (BPOM) Jakarta. Maintenance and treatment of experimental animals was carried out at Animal Research facilities, Indonesia Medical Education and Research Institute (IMERI), Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Indonesia.

The sample size was calculated using Federer's equation involving 6 treatment groups (see Study Design and Groups section). Based on these calculations, the minimum number of samples for each group is 4 rats. To account for the probability of mice dying before the completion of the study, the number of mice in each group was increased by one, bringing the total number of samples per group to five rats (a total of 30 mice).

Study design and groups

The research conducted was in vivo experimental research with a parallel design.

Animals were randomly divided into 6 treatment groups:

1. Normal group (N): normal rats and with no intervention.
2. Iron overload (IO) group: iron-overloaded rats treated with aquadest (negative control group).
3. Deferiprone group (D): iron-overloaded rats treated with deferiprone equivalent to the usual dose in humans (462.5 mg/kg BW).
4. PM fruit extract group (PM): iron-overloaded rats treated with PM fruit extract (100 mg/kg BW).
5. PM fruit extract+ deferiprone without dose reduction (DPM-1): iron-overloaded rats treated with the combination of PM fruit extract (100 mg/kg BW) and deferiprone (462.5 mg/kg BW).
6. PM fruit extract+ deferiprone with dose reduction (DPM-2): iron-overloaded rats treated with the combination of PM fruit extract (100 mg/kg BW) and deferiprone of half the usual dose (231.25 mg/kg BW).

The deferiprone dose for rats (462.5 mg/kg BW) was obtained through a mathematical calculation (human equivalent dose/HED formula). The dose was considered equivalent to the usual dose in humans (75 mg/kg BW) (Nair and Jacob 2016). Meanwhile, the dose for PM fruit extract (100 mg/kg BW) was selected based on previous research by Verna, which showed that PM fruit extract at the dose of 100 mg/kg BW can significantly lower plasma iron levels (Verna 2021).

Iron overload induction

Induction of iron overload in groups IO, D, PM, DPM-1, and DPM-2 was performed by injection of 0.3 mL iron dextran (containing 15 mg Fe) twice a week for 3 weeks

intraperitoneally. Based on previous research, the method was proven to increase plasma iron levels by up to 40× and increase ferritin levels by up to 10× higher than normal groups (Estuningtyas et al. 2018). After induction for 3 weeks, animals are given test substances according to their respective groups until the 8th week. Iron dextran administration continued until the study was completed at week 8 (Estuningtyas et al. 2018).

PM extract preparation

The PM fruit simplicia used in this study was obtained from PT Flozindo in Purwokerto, Central Java, Indonesia. The extract preparation was done according to Verna (2021). A total of 1000.05 g PM fruit simplicia was extracted by maceration technique using 70% ethanol. The ethanol in the crude extract was then evaporated using a rotary evaporator for 6 hours. The resulting concentrated extract was subsequently diluted with aquadest to obtain a stock solution with a concentration of 50 mg/mL.

Treatment

The test substances (vehicle, deferiprone, PM fruit extract, and a combination of deferiprone and PM fruit extract) were administered orally via gastric gavage once per day. The test substance was administered from the third week to the eighth week. The dose and volume of test substances administered to experimental animals are determined by body weight. For the DPM-1 and DPM-2 groups, the dose and volume of PM extract and deferiprone were estimated separately. Then, PM extract and deferiprone of the appropriate amount were added to the same microtube. The mixture was vortexed before administration.

Measurement of liver iron levels

Measurement of iron levels in the organ begins with the process of tissue destruction. Tissue samples weighing 500–1500 mg were placed in an Erlenmeyer tube and destroyed with 2 mL of HNO₃ and 1–2 drops of perchloric acid. Next, aquadest was added until the volume reached 50 mL. Fe concentration was measured using atomic absorbance spectrophotometry (AAS) at a wavelength of 248.3 nm (Estuningtyas et al. 2019).

Measurement of malondialdehyde (MDA) levels in the liver

MDA levels were measured by adding 1 mL of 20% TCA and 2 mL of 0.67% TBA to 200 µL of liver homogenate. The mixture was then heated at 100 °C for 10 minutes. Afterward, the sample was allowed to cool to room temperature and subsequently centrifuged at 3,000 rpm for 10 minutes. The supernatant was collected, and its absorbance was read at a wavelength of 530 nm. MDA levels were calculated using the regression equation derived from the standard curve.

Measurement of ALT and AST activity in plasma

ALT and AST activities in plasma were measured using a colorimetric assay (DSI, Cat. Nos.: 127019983021 and 126019983021). The measurement was based on the color change occurring after the sample was reacted with the appropriate substrate. Absorbance was recorded at the 1st, 2nd, 3rd, and 4th minutes at a wavelength of 365 nm. The difference in absorbance between the 1st and 4th minutes (ΔA) was recorded and then multiplied by a predetermined factor ($\times 3235$).

Measurement of mRNA GPx4 expression in the liver

GPx4 mRNA expression was measured using real-time PCR. RNA was isolated from liver homogenate using the Quick-RNA Miniprep Plus Kit (Zymo Research, Cat. No.: R1057). cDNA synthesis was performed with ReverTra Ace qPCR RT Master Mix with gDNA remover (Toyobo, Cat. No.: FSQ-301). Subsequently, RT-PCR was conducted to analyze GPx4 expression using the SensiFAST SYBR qPCR Mix (Bioline, Cat. No.: BIO-98005) with an annealing temperature of 60 °C. The primer sequences used in this study were designed by the Integrated Laboratory of the Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Indonesia. The GPx4 primers were GGAGCCAGGAAGTAATCAAGAA (forward) and CCTTGGGCTGGACTTTCAT (reverse), while the β -actin primers were ACAGGATGCAGAAGGAGATTAC (forward) and ACAGTGAGGCCAGGATAGA (reverse).

Measurement of GSH level in the liver

GSH levels were measured using a colorimetric method (Elabscience, Cat. No.: E-BC-K097-M). The measurement is based on the reaction of GSH with 5,5'-dithio-bis(2-nitrobenzoic acid) (DTNB), resulting in the formation of GSSG and 5'-thio-2-nitrobenzoic acid (TNB), which exhibits a yellow color. Optical density was measured at a wavelength of 412 nm.

Measurement of TNF- α level in the liver

TNF- α levels in liver tissue were measured using an ELISA method (Cusabio, Cat. No.: CSB-E11987r) according to the manufacturer's instructions.

Histopathological examination of liver tissue

The left lobe of the liver was fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin. Subsequent processing involved paraffin embedding and staining with hematoxylin and eosin, Prussian blue, and Masson's trichrome. Hematoxylin and eosin staining were performed to assess inflammation. Inflammation was evaluated by counting the number of inflammatory foci in five fields of view at 200×

magnification (Yoo et al. 2019). Prussian blue staining was utilized to assess iron accumulation in the liver. The stained area was quantified using ImageJ software by adjusting the threshold to accurately select the iron accumulation regions. This was then compared to the total area to determine the percentage of stained area. Analysis was performed in five fields of view at 200× magnification (Hyon et al. 2011; Abo-Elghiet et al. 2023). Masson's trichrome staining was employed to evaluate the presence or absence of fibrosis.

Statistical analysis

Data analysis was conducted using SPSS version 27. Normality was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test, while homogeneity was evaluated using Levene's test. Data that were normally distributed are presented as mean ± standard deviation, whereas non-normally distributed data are presented as median, minimum, and maximum values. Normally distributed and homogeneous data were analyzed using one-way ANOVA followed by post-hoc LSD tests. For normally distributed but heterogeneous data, Welch's ANOVA with post-hoc Games-Howell tests was employed. Data that were not normally distributed were transformed using Log10. If normality was not achieved, Kruskal-Wallis tests followed by pair-wise comparisons with Bonferroni correction were used. Statistical significance was considered at $p < 0.05$. Data visualization was performed using GraphPad Prism 9.

Results

Iron levels and area of iron accumulation in the liver

Iron overload induction in this study resulted in a significant increase in liver iron levels in the IO group compared to the N group ($p = 0.032$). Although statistically

non-significant, the DPM-2 group exhibited lower iron levels compared to the IO group, while other treatment groups showed higher average iron levels than the IO group. Consistent with liver iron measurements, histopathological examination revealed a significant increase in iron accumulation in the IO group compared to the N group. Among the iron overload groups receiving treatment, only the DPM-2 group demonstrated a significant reduction in iron accumulation compared to the IO group (Figs 1, 2).

Liver MDA levels and plasma ALT and AST activities

Iron overload induction in this study led to a significant increase in liver MDA levels in the IO group compared to the N group ($p = 0.032$). Although no statistically significant differences were observed, all treatment groups exhibited a greater increase in MDA levels compared to the IO group ($p > 0.05$). Among the treatment groups, the DPM-2 group showed the lowest liver MDA levels (Fig. 3).

An increase in MDA levels in the IO group was not accompanied by a significant rise in ALT and AST activities compared to the N group ($p = 0.572$). Nevertheless, the IO group showed higher average ALT and AST activities compared to the N group. ALT activity in the treatment groups did not show significant differences from the IO group ($p > 0.05$). Among the treatment groups, only the PM group exhibited lower average ALT and AST activities compared to the IO group, though this difference was not statistically significant. Conversely, groups receiving deferiprone, whether alone (D) or in combination with PM fruit extract (DPM-1 and DPM-2), showed higher average ALT and AST activities compared to the IO group. The increase in AST in these groups was statistically significant compared to the negative control group. Among these three groups, the DPM-2 group had lower ALT and AST activities compared to the D and DPM-1 groups (Fig. 3).

Figure 1. Comparison of liver iron levels and percentage of iron accumulation area at week 8. N: normal; IO: iron overload; D: IO+deferiprone; PM: IO+ PM fruit extract 100 mg/kg BW; DPM-1: IO+ deferiprone 462,5 mg/kg BW + PM fruit extract 100 mg/kg BW; DPM-2: IO + deferiprone 231,25 mg/kg BW + PM fruit extract 100 mg/kg BW. * $p < 0,05$ vs N; # $p < 0,05$ vs IO.

Figure 2. Liver histopathology with Prussian blue staining at 200× magnification. The normal group exhibits normal liver anatomy with no iron accumulation (a). The iron overload groups, including IO (b), D (c), PM (d), DPM-1 (e), and DPM-2 (f), show iron accumulation indicated by areas of blue staining (white arrows). CV: central vein; PT: portal tract; S: sinusoid. Scale bar: 50 μm.

Figure 3. Comparison of liver MDA levels and plasma ALT and AST activities at week 8. N: normal; IO: iron overload; D: IO+deferiprone; PM: IO+ PM fruit extract 100 mg/kg BW; DPM-1: IO+ deferiprone 462,5 mg/kg BW + PM fruit extract 100 mg/kg BW; DPM-2: IO + deferiprone 231,25 mg/kg BW + PM fruit extract 100 mg/kg BW. *p < 0,05 vs N; #p < 0,05 vs IO.

GPx4 mRNA expression and GSH level in the liver

The analysis of GPx4 mRNA expression was performed by comparing the expression levels of GPx4 mRNA with the housekeeping gene β -actin. The results revealed that the GPx4 mRNA expression in the IO group was not significantly different from the N group ($p > 0.05$), though the IO group exhibited a higher expression compared to the N group. Similarly, there were no significant differences in the GPx4 mRNA expression between the treatment groups (D, PM, DPM-1, and DPM-2) and the IO group ($p > 0.05$). However, the treatment groups showed lower GPx4 mRNA expression compared to the IO group. In contrast, liver GSH levels were generally higher in the iron-overloaded groups compared to the N group (Fig. 4).

TNF- α levels and number of inflammatory foci in the liver

The assessment of inflammation through TNF- α levels was consistent with histopathological findings. The liver TNF- α levels in the IO group did not differ significantly from those in the N group ($p = 0.457$). However, the IO group exhibited a higher mean TNF- α level compared to the N group. Among the therapy groups, the PM group showed the highest mean TNF- α levels compared to the IO group. Histopathological examination also revealed that the PM group had the highest median number of inflammatory foci (Figs 5, 6). Conversely, the DPM-2 group had the lowest TNF- α levels among all groups (Fig. 5).

Histopathological evaluation of liver fibrosis

Fibrosis was evaluated using Masson's trichrome staining. In this study, no fibrosis was observed in any of the treatment groups. Connective tissue was only noted around blood vessels within normal limits (Fig. 7).

Discussion

Iron overload in this study was induced through intraperitoneal injection of iron-dextran to mimic conditions of repeated blood transfusion-related iron accumulation. This induction method effectively increased iron accumulation in the liver, as evidenced by both atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS) and histopathological examination, yielding consistent results. Iron overload induction in this study led to a fivefold increase in liver iron levels in the untreated iron-overload group compared to the normal group, with an accumulation area of approximately 6.55%.

In this study, iron accumulation primarily occurred in Kupffer cells and within the sinusoidal spaces. This observation aligns with other studies on the distribution and histopathological characteristics of iron overload induced through intraperitoneal iron-dextran injection. Yatmark et al. (2014) reported that parenteral iron administration leads to iron deposition predominantly in phagocytic cells, such as Kupffer cells, and in the sinusoidal spaces. The iron accumulation was also uniformly distributed throughout the liver. Additionally, hemosiderin granules were observed in the hepatocyte cytoplasm, albeit to a lesser extent (Yatmark et al. 2014).

In this study, the increase in iron levels in the IO group was accompanied by a significant rise in MDA concentration, nearly doubling compared to the normal group. These findings are consistent with research by Al-Basher (2019) and Li et al. (2021), which observed elevated MDA levels associated with increased hepatic iron content. MDA serves as a marker for lipid peroxidation (Ding et al. 2021). Iron contributes to lipid peroxidation through two mechanisms: the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) via the Fenton reaction (non-enzymatic peroxidation) and the enhancement of lipoxygenase (LOX) enzyme activity (enzymatic lipid peroxidation) (Dixon and Pratt 2023; Jin et al. 2024). Free radicals can attack the double bonds between carbon atoms in polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs), leading to the formation of lipid hydroperoxides. These hydroperoxides are unstable and subsequently degrade into secondary aldehyde products, such as MDA (Zhang et al. 2023).

Figure 4. Comparison of GPx4 mRNA Expression and Liver GSH Levels at Week 8. N: normal; IO: iron overload; D: IO+deferiprone; PM: IO+ PM fruit extract 100 mg/kg BW; DPM-1: IO+ deferiprone 462,5 mg/kg BW + PM fruit extract 100 mg/kg BW; DPM-2: IO + deferiprone 231,25 mg/kg BW + PM fruit extract 100 mg/kg BW. * $p < 0,05$ vs N; # $p < 0,05$ vs IO.

Figure 5. Comparison of TNF- α levels and the number of inflammatory foci in the liver at week 8. N: normal; IO: iron overload; D: IO+deferiprone; PM: IO+PM fruit extract 100 mg/kg BW; DPM-1: IO+ deferiprone 462,5 mg/kg BW + PM fruit extract 100 mg/kg BW; DPM-2: IO + deferiprone 231,25 mg/kg BW + PM fruit extract 100 mg/kg BW. * $p < 0,05$ vs N; # $p < 0,05$ vs IO.

Figure 6. Liver histopathology with hematoxylin-eosin staining at 200 \times magnification (left panel) and 400 \times magnification (right panel). The normal group showed normal morphology with limited inflammation in the periportal region and no iron accumulation (a). The iron-overloaded groups, including IO (b), D (c), PM (d), DPM-1 (e), and DPM-2 (f), showed infiltration of inflammatory cells around the iron deposits, which appear brownish (white arrows). CV: central vein; PT: portal tract. Scale bar: 50 μ m.

Figure 7. Liver histopathology with Masson's trichrome staining at 40× magnification (left panel) and 400× magnification (right panel). All groups display normal connective tissue surrounding blood vessels (white arrows). **a** N; **b** IO; **c** D; **d** PM; **e** DPM-1; **f** DPM-2. Scale bar: 200 μ m (left); 50 μ m (right).

Despite these findings, the increase in iron and MDA levels in the untreated iron-overloaded group was not accompanied by a significant rise in ALT and AST levels. This data suggests that although elevated iron levels may lead to lipid peroxidation and increased MDA formation, it does not necessarily result in significant membrane

rupture. This may be due to the lipid peroxidation not reaching a threshold sufficient to induce ferroptosis, possibly because of protective effects from antioxidant systems that prevent further peroxidation. This is supported by the observation that GPx4 mRNA expression in the IO group was twice that of the normal group, accompanied

by a 23.94% increase in GSH levels. Although these increases were not statistically significant, GPx4 and GSH are crucial antioxidants that reduce lipid hydroperoxides to non-toxic lipid alcohols, thereby inhibiting the propagation of lipid peroxidation and preventing ferroptosis (Pope and Dixon 2023).

In line with the findings of this study, Ding et al. (2021) also reported an increase in GPx4 levels in the liver of mice following parenteral iron overload induction. The elevation in GSH and GPx4 mRNA may occur as a response to increased ROS levels. Gong et al. (2019) demonstrated that increased ROS induces elevated GPx4 expression as a response to lipid peroxidation. Wu et al. (2021) reported that GSH levels also increase in response to elevated ROS. This rise in GSH is believed to be a compensatory mechanism mediated by increased expression of SLC7A11. SLC7A11 is a key component of the cystine/glutamate antiporter system that regulates GSH synthesis. The increase in ROS due to iron overload induces enhanced cystine uptake into cells for GSH synthesis (Wu et al. 2021). A decrease in GSH levels and GPx4 expression occurs only after ROS levels have been persistently elevated (Gong et al. 2019).

In this study, administration of deferiprone at a dose of 462.5 mg/kg BW once daily for 5 weeks did not effectively reduce liver iron levels in iron-overloaded rats. This finding aligns with previous research. Yatmark et al. (2014) demonstrated that deferiprone was ineffective in lowering liver iron levels in mice subjected to parenteral iron overload. The average liver iron concentration in the deferiprone-treated group in their study was 17.3 ± 2.2 mg/g tissue, compared to 15.6 ± 2.0 mg/g tissue in the iron-overloaded group without therapy (Yatmark et al. 2014).

The inability of deferiprone to reduce liver iron levels in this study may be related to its metabolic processes in the liver. Deferiprone metabolism involves glucuronidation at the iron-binding sites (Vlachodimitropoulou Koumoutsou 2017). The metabolite produced, deferiprone glucuronide, lacks the ability to chelate iron and is subsequently excreted via the urine (Heli et al. 2011). In vitro research by Vlachodimitropoulou Koumoutsou (2017) has demonstrated that deferiprone is more effective at mobilizing iron from cardiomyocytes compared to hepatocytes. This is attributed to the fact that liver cells contain enzymes responsible for the metabolism of deferiprone, whereas cardiac cells do not.

The elevated iron levels observed in the deferiprone group were accompanied by a significant increase in MDA levels, surpassing those in the untreated group. Specifically, MDA levels in the deferiprone group were three times higher than those in the normal group. Additionally, this group exhibited greater increases in ALT and AST levels compared to the untreated group, with ALT rising threefold and AST increasing 2.8 times compared to the normal group. These findings suggest that lipid peroxidation and hepatocellular damage are more pronounced in the deferiprone group compared to the untreated group. This exacerbated damage may be due to the elevated iron levels

not being matched by a corresponding increase in GPx4 mRNA expression. In fact, GPx4 mRNA expression decreased by approximately 18% in the deferiprone group compared to the normal group. According to Wu et al. (2021), although there was an increase in GSH levels in this group, it was insufficient to compensate for the reduced GPx4 levels, leading to continued lipid peroxidation.

Gong et al. (2019) demonstrated that a decrease in GPx4 can occur due to an increase in ROS and persistent lipid peroxidation. Wu et al. (2021) indicated that elevated iron levels, such as those observed in the deferiprone group in this study, can inhibit Nrf2 phosphorylation, leading to a reduction in GPx4 expression. Nrf2 is a key transcription factor involved in regulating cellular oxidative stress by controlling the expression of over 200 antioxidant genes, including GPx4 (Xiang et al. 2024).

The administration of an ethanol extract of PM fruit (100 mg/kg BW) in this study was not effective in reducing liver iron concentrations. These findings are consistent with the results reported by Verna, who demonstrated that ethanol extract of PM fruit at a dose of 100 mg/kg BW failed to decrease liver iron levels in iron-overloaded rats. In Verna's study, the average liver iron concentration following extract administration was 78.11 ± 12.72 mg Fe/g, compared to 78.00 ± 9.22 mg Fe/g in the untreated control group (Verna 2021). This may be related to the pharmacokinetics of the compounds present in the extract.

To elicit a biological effect, a compound must reach its target site at an adequate concentration and persist for a sufficient duration. Therefore, an ideal oral chelator should be efficiently absorbed through the gastrointestinal tract, possess the ability to permeate biological membranes to reach the desired target site, such as the liver, and have a slow metabolic process. (Crisponi and Remelli 2008; Ma et al. 2012; Yang et al. 2020a). The greater the lipophilicity of a compound, the larger its volume of distribution. This property is crucial for compounds expected to exert their effects within cells (Panchagnula and Thomas 2000).

The ethanol extract of PM fruit contains several compounds that have been shown to chelate iron, including mangiferin (Estuningtyas et al. 2018, 2019) and various flavonoids such as epigallocatechin-3-gallate (EGCG) (Thephinlap et al. 2007), naringenin, kaempferol, apigenin, and taxifolin (Mladěnka et al. 2011). The oral bioavailability of mangiferin is reported to be around 1–5%. This is primarily due to its poor solubility in water. Additionally, mangiferin's lipophilicity is relatively low, which impairs its ability to cross the gastrointestinal membranes. Mangiferin also undergoes significant first-pass metabolism and efflux by P-glycoprotein (P-gp) transporters. Furthermore, mangiferin is metabolized rapidly, resulting in a shorter half-life (Barakat et al. 2022; Zivković et al. 2024). In addition to shortening its half-life, the metabolism of mangiferin through glucuronidation results in the formation of metabolites that lack the ability to chelate iron, leading to a loss of its antioxidant effects (van der Merwe et al. 2012). This process may also contribute to the reduced efficacy of the extract in lowering liver iron levels,

as the enzymes responsible for this metabolic process are abundantly present in hepatocytes (Vlachodimitropoulou Koumoutsea 2017).

Phenolic compounds, such as flavonoids, also exhibit low absorption and limited oral bioavailability due to their poor solubility in water and instability within the gastrointestinal tract. Upon entering cells, phenolic compounds can undergo efflux processes and return to the intestinal lumen due to the presence of efflux transporters on the apical membrane of epithelial cells, including P-glycoprotein (P-gp), multidrug resistance-associated proteins (MRPs), and breast cancer resistance proteins (BCRPs) (Li et al. 2015). For example, the bioavailability of EGCG is only approximately 0.1–0.3% (Pervin et al. 2019). The low bioavailability of EGCG is attributed to its instability under the acidic conditions of the stomach and the relatively neutral pH of the intestines, leading to its degradation. Additionally, EGCG undergoes efflux processes mediated by transporters (Li et al. 2015).

The high iron levels in the PM group were also accompanied by a significantly higher increase in MDA levels compared to the untreated group. The increase in MDA in the PM group reached nearly three times (2.97-fold) that of the normal group. Similar to other groups, this elevated MDA level may be attributed to the persistently high iron content in the tissue. However, the study findings indicate that although iron levels in the PM group were higher than in the deferiprone group, the increase in MDA in the PM group was not as pronounced as in the deferiprone group. This discrepancy may be attributed to the antioxidant properties inherent in the ethanolic extract of PM fruit.

Lim et al. (2019) demonstrated that the ethanol extract of PM fruit exhibits higher antioxidant activity compared to water and methanol extracts. Ethanol is the most efficient solvent for extracting mangiferin as well as phenolic compounds and flavonoids from PM fruit. Mangiferin has been shown to directly scavenge free radicals (Kullu et al. 2014). Additionally, Sasangka (2022) revealed that the ethanol extract used in this study also contains other compounds such as EGCG, apigenin, and kaempferol, which have similar free radical scavenging abilities (Boulmoukh et al. 2021; Tian et al. 2021). Despite these findings, the antioxidant effects of the extract have not led to a significant reduction in MDA levels in liver tissues. This may be attributed to pharmacokinetic factors. For instance, the glucuronidation of mangiferin not only removes its ability to chelate iron but also results in the loss of its antioxidant capacity (van der Merwe et al. 2012).

The activity of ALT and AST in the PM group did not differ significantly from the normal group. Similar to the untreated group, this may be because the lipid peroxidation has not reached the threshold necessary for cell rupture. However, this protective effect does not seem to stem from modulation of GPx4 expression, as the mRNA expression of GPx4 in this group decreased by 50.48% compared to the normal group. This reduction in GPx4 mRNA expression is comparable to that observed in the deferiprone group and may be due to the high iron lev-

els. Elevated iron levels can inhibit Nrf2 phosphorylation and lead to decreased GPx4 expression (Wu et al. 2021). Therefore, the hepatoprotective effects observed in this group may be attributed to alternative mechanisms.

Although GPx4 is a primary antioxidant system capable of preventing ferroptosis, other mechanisms also influence cellular sensitivity to ferroptosis that do not rely on GPx4. One such mechanism is FSP1. The loss of GPx4 activity can activate alternative compensatory mechanisms to counteract increased ROS, one of which is FSP1. Research by Doll et al. (2019) has demonstrated that FSP1 can prevent ferroptosis in cells with GPx4 deletion. The anti-ferroptotic effect of FSP1 is related to its role in catalyzing the regeneration of ubiquinone (coenzyme Q10). Ubiquinone, in its reduced form, ubiquinol, can scavenge lipid peroxyl radicals that mediate lipid peroxidation (Doll et al. 2019). Additionally, FSP1 plays a role in recruiting ESCRT-III, a membrane repair system that helps protect cells from the effects of lipid peroxidation and prevents ferroptosis, to the plasma membrane (Wang et al. 2020).

The group receiving the combination of ethanolic extract of PM fruit and deferiprone exhibited a lower liver iron content compared to monotherapy with the extract alone. This reduction in iron levels was more pronounced when the deferiprone dose was reduced to half of the standard dose. The combination of an ethanolic extract of PM fruit with half the standard dose of deferiprone resulted in a 44.51% reduction in liver iron content compared to the untreated group. This indicates a synergistic effect when deferiprone and the ethanolic extract of PM fruit are administered together, particularly when the deferiprone dose is reduced.

The precise reason for the enhanced iron chelation effect observed with the reduced deferiprone dose in the combination group is not clearly understood in this study. Typically, when drugs are combined in a specific ratio, they are considered a new therapeutic entity, exhibiting a unique dose-response relationship when assessed in cellular and tissue contexts. The therapeutic efficacy of combination therapy is influenced not only by the inherent properties of the individual drugs but also by the specific dosage ratio employed. Therefore, research on synergy should focus not only on determining whether a combination exhibits synergistic effects but also on identifying the optimal ratio required to achieve such synergy (Tallarida 2011; Ma and Motsinger-Reif 2019). In the present study, it is evident that the combination of ethanolic extract of PM fruit (100 mg/kg) with half the standard dose of deferiprone yields a more optimal effect than the combination without dose reduction.

The synergistic effect observed from the combination of ethanolic extract of PM fruit and deferiprone might be explained by the hypothesis of iron shuttling. The shuttle hypothesis posits that various chelators possess differing iron-binding capacities and distinct abilities to access iron from various cellular compartments. Chelators with better penetration, such as deferiprone, can bind intracellular iron and transport it into the circulation. Once in circu-

lation, the iron bound by deferiprone can be sequestered by a second chelator with a higher iron-binding capacity, such as deferoxamine, allowing the first chelator to be freed and resume its function (Aydinok 2023). Research by Vlachodimitropoulou Koumoutsea (2017) indicates that the synergistic effect for cellular iron removal can only occur if at least one of the chelators has physico-chemical properties that enable cellular entry.

Based on the research by Sasangka (2022), the ethanolic extract of PM fruit used in this study contains epigallocatechin-3-gallate (EGCG). In the study by Settakorn et al. (2022), although not statistically significant, the combination of EGCG and deferiprone showed lower levels and scores of iron accumulation compared to monotherapy. Deferiprone is thought to act as a shuttle, mobilizing intracellular iron and transporting it out of the cell. Once outside the cell, deferiprone transfers the iron to EGCG, which then chelates the iron from deferiprone using its diol-phenolic groups.

The reduction pattern in the MDA levels and ALT and AST activities in the combination group corresponds to liver iron levels. Rats treated with a combination of the ethanolic extract of PM fruit and half-dose deferiprone showed the most favorable results. These findings suggest that reducing the deferiprone dose can decrease lipid peroxidation and ferroptosis. In this study, although both deferiprone monotherapy and the ethanolic extract of PM fruit monotherapy resulted in increased MDA levels, the extract monotherapy did not significantly elevate ALT and AST levels. In contrast, deferiprone monotherapy caused substantial increases in ALT and AST. Therefore, it is not surprising that the combination therapy led to reduced ALT and AST levels, possibly due to the protective effects from the extract.

When considering the levels of GSH and the expression of mRNA GPx4, the combination group, like all groups subjected to iron overload, exhibited an increase in GSH and a decrease in mRNA GPx4 expression that were not significantly different from those of the normal group. Consequently, the observed reductions in MDA, ALT, and AST levels in the combination group are likely not mediated by GPx4 modulation. Instead, they may result from decreased iron levels, the protective effects of the ethanolic extract of PM fruit, and/or the reduction in deferiprone dosage.

The histopathological assessment of inflammation in the liver is in agreement with the TNF- α level measurements in the same organ. Although not statistically significant, the iron overload group exhibited higher TNF- α levels and a greater median focus of inflammation compared to the normal group. Infiltration of inflammatory cells in the iron overload group was predominantly observed around areas of iron accumulation. These findings are consistent with Zhang et al. (2013), who reported inflammatory foci at sites of iron deposition. Iron can activate Kupffer cells and induce the chemotaxis of mononuclear cells to areas of damage (Yatmark et al. 2014). The accumulation of macrophages and Kupffer cells represents a compensatory mechanism to phagocytize excess iron (Yamauchi et al. 2019). Previous studies have demonstrated that iron supplementation in rat Kupffer cell cultures

activates NF- κ B, enhances TNF- α promoter activity, and increases TNF- α protein levels (She et al. 2002).

In the group treated with deferiprone, the increase in iron levels, MDA, ALT, and AST was not accompanied by a corresponding rise in TNF- α levels compared to the untreated group. In fact, TNF- α levels in the deferiprone group were notably lower than those in the negative control group. This observation suggests that deferiprone may exert a suppressive effect on TNF- α under conditions of iron overload. This finding aligns with the results of Verma (2021), which indicated a reduction in TNF- α levels in iron-overloaded rats following deferiprone administration. Deferiprone has been documented to possess anti-inflammatory properties, as evidenced by Zou et al. (2017), who reported that deferiprone administration led to decreased mRNA and protein levels of NF- κ B in a diabetic cardiomyopathy rat model.

Monotherapy with the ethanolic extract of PM fruit resulted in the highest TNF- α levels among the groups studied. However, in this group, ALT and AST levels were relatively lower compared to those in the negative control and other treatment groups. This suggests that the inflammation, as indicated by elevated TNF- α levels in this group, is likely not attributed to cell death but rather to the higher iron levels observed compared to other groups. These findings imply that the ethanolic extract of PM fruit was insufficient in mitigating inflammation associated with iron overload. Despite containing various compounds with known anti-inflammatory properties, such as mangiferin, apigenin, and EGCG, which have been shown to reduce TNF- α levels in different conditions, the extract did not effectively lower TNF- α in this context (Saha et al. 2016; Yue et al. 2020; Xu et al. 2023). Similar to its limited efficacy in iron chelation, the reduced anti-inflammatory effect of the ethanolic extract of PM fruit may also be attributed to its low bioavailability and lipophilicity.

Conversely, the administration of the ethanolic extract of PM fruit in combination with deferiprone resulted in a lower TNF- α level compared to monotherapy with the extract alone. This observation suggests that the reduction in TNF- α is not solely due to decreased iron levels but also reflects the anti-inflammatory effects of deferiprone.

Histopathological examination using Masson's trichrome staining did not reveal any evidence of fibrosis in any of the groups, whether treated or untreated. This lack of observed fibrosis may be related to both the dose and the duration of the induction being insufficient to cause fibrosis. In this study, iron overload was induced by iron-dextran injections over 8 weeks with a total dose of 240 mg. Brown et al. (2003) demonstrated that an iron-dextran injection with a total dose of 900 mg administered over 22 weeks was still insufficient to induce fibrosis in rats. They noted that fibrosis might occur with extended induction duration. Unlike humans, mice and rats have a higher tolerance for high doses of iron. It is hypothesized that these rodents possess iron excretion mechanisms that provide protection against iron overload-induced organ damage, making such damage less likely to occur (Oates et al. 2000; Musumeci et al. 2014).

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that the administration of the ethanolic extract of PM fruit (100 mg/kg body weight) in combination with deferiprone at half the standard dose effectively reduces hepatic iron levels by 44.51%. This combination therapy also tends to decrease MDA levels in the liver and activity of ALT and AST in plasma, while increasing GSH levels in the liver and reducing inflammation, as evidenced by the greatest reduction in TNF- α levels in hepatic tissue. However, this combined therapy does not significantly modulate mRNA expression of GPx4 in the liver. Histopathological examination reveals that the combination of the ethanolic extract of PM fruit (100 mg/kg BW) with deferiprone at half the standard dose significantly reduces iron accumulation but does not reduce the number of inflammatory foci. In the future, we hope that the findings of this study will provide valuable insights into the potential use of Indonesian natural products, particularly *Phaleria macrocarpa* fruit, as an adjuvant therapy for iron overload conditions. The combination of PM extract with deferiprone is expected to address some of the challenges associated with using deferiprone alone by enhancing iron chelation and providing hepatoprotective effects.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

Experiments on animals: the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Medicine, University of Indonesia-Cipto Mangunkusumo Hospital (No. KET964/UN2.F1/ETIK/PPM.00.02/2022)

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Author contributions

Ari Estuningtyas: study design and conceptualization, funding acquisition, data analysis, manuscript writing. Rahma: data collection and analysis, manuscript writing. Kusmardi: supervision in histopathological analysis, data analysis, manuscript writing. Erni Hernawati Poerwaningsih: supervision in extract preparation, manuscript writing.

Author ORCIDs

Ari Estuningtyas <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4093-4871>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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